

EPOS SP – Grant Agreement n. 871121

D1.5 – Final report on KPIs and risks monitoring to internal boards

Document Information Summary

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Executive Summary

The EPOS SP Risk Register has been delivered (D1.2 Risk Register) at M3, April 2020.

D1.5 "Final report on KPIs and risks monitoring to internal boards" (M30) is an update of D.1.4 "First report on KPIs and risks monitoring to internal boards" (M12) that has been delivered on January 2021 (M12). In particular, the update concerns the status of the EPOS SP risks and KPIs at M30, assessed after the M19-27 interim report.

The report has been drafted by the EPOS ERIC Executive Coordination Office (ECO) with the contribution of the WP Leaders. D1.5 is planned in the framework of the WP1 "Project Management", Task 1.3 "Risk Management and project impact assessment" focusing on ensuring an adequate quality control mechanism to manage the project impact and risks.

During the project's lifetime, periodic assessments of the state of the play of the project's key performance indicators (KPIs) and risks have been performed within each WPs and at Executive Board (EB) level. Corrective actions have been defined when the performance, quality, or effectiveness of the activities executed were not achieved. Risk mitigation and contingency measures were planned to be implemented if needed.

The final report on KPIs and risks monitoring to internal boards aims to support the EPOS SP Boards namely, the Executive Board, the Project Council, and the Advisory Board, to guarantee the effective management of KPIs and risks and propose timely corrective actions for the effective implementation and prosecution of the project.

Introduction

To ensure high-quality results of the project, it is essential to monitor the risks, the performance, quality, and effectiveness of the activities executed on regular bases to define timely corrective actions for ensuring a proper and successful prosecution of the project. Therefore, since the beginning of the project high relevance has been dedicated to risk identification and management. The Executive Board (EB) carefully assessed risks associated with COVID-19, and adequate mitigation actions have been identified.

Furthermore, on the 22nd of April 2021 (M15), during the 2nd Advisory Board (AB) meeting, the ECO presented the EPOS SP Risk Register and Key Performance Indicators definition and monitoring process to the EPOS SP Advisory Board. In particular, the AB acknowledged D1.4 “First report on KPIs and risk monitoring to internal boards” which mainly reported difficulties related to the COVID-19 pandemic restrictions, particularly concerning planned engagement activities, and the reduced exposure of dissemination activities, including the additional workload resulting from the new work modalities. The comments and recommendations from the Advisory Board Members for the project management, are reported in the AB report covering the period from 01/02/2020 to 31/01/2021; they state the following: “The AB acknowledges the flawless execution of the project management and the quality control of the outputs delivered so far. Procedures appear to have been appropriately implemented and effective. The KPIs are substantially in line with the Objectives. The Risk Register seems to be considering and effectively monitoring the risks, and it has adequately been integrated with unforeseen risks related to the COVID-19 pandemic, focusing on the delay in achieving milestones and submitting deliverables.”.

Finally, during the 10th EB meeting on February 3rd, 2022, the “Key performance indicator and risk register updated month 24” has been approved (**Milestone 21**). As was in the first year of the project, also in the second year, risks resulting from the COVID-19 pandemic have been particularly monitored. It impacted some project activities by delaying actions linked to the stakeholders’ engagement and international cooperation, but not affecting the project results that are in line with the planned ones.

The following paragraphs describe the results of the monitoring of KPIs, and the risks associated with the project’s work plan at M27 to achieve the project objectives successfully.

1. Monitoring of the EPOS SP Key Performance Indicators M27

Each Work Package (WP) Leader is responsible for updating the proposed KPIs, objectives, purpose, and measurement tools periodically. The KPIs classification and assessment at M27 are provided within the current document (Annex I). In particular, the assessment of the performance indicators undertaken at M27 at the WP level, reports the following main concepts, considering the aims of each WP.

WP1 Project Management aims to ensure the project's success through adequate management and quality control mechanisms and efficient and proactive interaction with the European Commission. At M9, W1 reached the objectives for the period, with no delay. At M27, the only slight deviance refers to the percentage of milestones achieved on time (KPI 1.1). This depends on the fact that some of the activities of the project have been rescheduled due to COVID-19. For this reason, some milestones have been also rescheduled

accordingly with the new requested end date of the project. The request for the amendment of the Grant agreement is currently under evaluation by the European Commission, Research Executive Agency (REA).

WP2 Governance and Financial Framework aims to undertake activities to strengthen financial sustainability in a context coherent with the EPOS ERIC governance; at M9, WP2 performance was in line with the period's objectives. At M27, WP2 reports that Covid-19 restrictions made difficult the organisation of initiatives in the Baltic Region. Integration of the virtual communication tools in the implementation of WP2 activities has been planned as a corrective action to engage scientists and other stakeholders including data providers from solid Earth science in the Adriatic-Balkans-Dinarides Region (ABDarray).

It is relevant to mention activities related to KPI 2.1 “number of engaged national authorities from countries previously involved in EPOS but not yet ERIC members”; the first action in this direction has been the establishment of a National Authorities Consulting Board (NACB) composed of representatives of those countries not yet involved in EPOS ERIC. Currently, NACB Members are representative of the following countries: Bulgaria, Finland, Germany, Ireland, Slovak Republic, and Spain. NACB Observers are Representative of the following countries: Austria, Czech Republic, Hungary, and Turkey. Two further countries have been engaged outside NACB through communication with national scientific communities and dedicated WP2 brokerage initiatives: namely, Sweden and Croatia. This can be considered a relevant result reached in the framework of task 2.1 of the EPOS SP project.

Furthermore, the landscape analysis has been completed in the framework of task 2.2, together with a series of interactions with TCS, that created the conditions to implement deliverable 2.4 at M33.

These results and the ongoing work on the implementation of the TCS cost-book and EPOS ERIC sustainability have ensured progress in task 2.3 for wat concern indication on the EPOS ERIC financial plan.

In conclusion, WP2 is on track with its activity plan to deliver WP8 the necessary achievements and information to feed the EPOS sustainability report.

WP3 Global Dimension, European and International Cooperation aims to expand the EPOS global dimension of EPOS and foster international cooperation with other research infrastructures, Earth science and e-science initiatives, including those in other global regions.

At M9, WP3 informed indicted that it would be premature to measure its related KPIs. At M27, WP3 reported a delay in its planned activities, where were based on in-person interactions with external stakeholders, due to the impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic. In recent months several of the planned engagement events have been reshaped and rescheduled, and a revised schedule of WP3 activities across all tasks will be drafted by September 2022. This updated programme of activities will commence with the 1st EPOS International conference that is being organised in Cape Verde on 11 – 13 July 2022, and the announcement of details for the 2nd EPOS International Conference will be made soon (KPI 3.6).

WP4 Increasing Value for Users aims to create awareness and trust in the users of the EPOS provision and engage new users and scientific communities in EPOS. At M9 and M27, WP4 assessment confirms KPIs are mostly on track with the planned objectives.

WP5 Strengthening links with Private Sector aims to foster sustainable and ethically coherent cooperation with industry and SMEs. At M9, WP5 reported a delay in its activities mainly due to COVID-19 Pandemic. At

M9, WP5 activities were mostly interaction activities with the private sector. WP5 informed the coordinator that was premature to measure the KPIs at that stage.

Concerning M27 monitoring and assessment, during the WP5 Task Leader Meeting organized on 2nd June 2022 the decision has been taken to redefine measures of WP5 performance. The initially proposed Key Performance Indicators assumed that the services of pilot areas will be developed and implemented at the beginning of the project and there will be many direct contacts with the private sector to promote EPOS assets. Additionally, KPIs were proposed assuming that AAAI service on ICS-C will be fully implemented. Due to the Covid-19 pandemic many activities have been prevented or delayed in the past two years. Moreover, at the moment EPOS does not authenticate users as they access the website, technically the website is not yet in production use; the target is end-June 2022 for the EPOS community. ICS does authenticate users when they utilize the workspace to access services. The TCS representatives have just agreed on the information they wish ICS to provide to TCS concerning users and ICS had an IT team meeting end-May to discuss how to implement this issue. Once implemented ICS should be able to provide statistics on usage by class of user, country etc. Considering the involvement of TCSs to gather the statistics of the use of the services with the innovation potential it is also not the proper direction to root the KPI since different asset suppliers in each TCS have different methods of authentication/authorizing users and creating statistics. They have users from various initial network points, not only ICS-C. The problem also refers to the EPOS website where the research and innovation service is proposed to be implemented. The idea was that commercial users would be just like any other user of EPOS, although the authentication and authorization may be different and the licensing conditions for the assets may be different (reflected in the authorization of authenticated user against the asset metadata. So far there are no technical mechanisms allowing us to implement the defined earlier KPIs. To ensure that the WP5 workflow is properly set up and it is efficient to achieve the final goals we propose to define new measures of WP5 performance with the focus on three main fields: (1) mechanisms for communicating the EPOS innovation potential, KPIs: 5.1.1 - 5.1.4, (2) action to build the governance/legal framework, KPIs: 5.2.1 – 5.2.3, and (3) strategy and plan for boosting EPOS to measure the effect of innovation activity utilization, KPIs: 5.3.1 – 5.3.3.

WP6 Value for Society deals with society's societal benefits of the EPOS Delivery Framework in an ethically coherent framework. Due to the nature of its activities, WP6 KPIs are qualitative indicators. M9 and M27 assessments proved they are in line with the key performance expectations. A delay on the activities related to Tasks 6.3 “EPOS readiness for Open Science” in order to adhere to FAIR principles are delayed due to lead beneficiary staff shortages due to BREXIT but WP6 is in the process of formulating a set of diverse recommendations and a plan to complete the actions have been implemented and communicated to the EB.

WP7 Outreach and Training aims to foster dissemination, outreach and training on the use of the EPOS data and service provision for different stakeholder categories and target audiences. As it was at M9, and also at M27, the KPIs assessment provides that several virtual events have been organised, keeping WP performance high. WP7 identified corrective actions consisting of managing the meetings and training events virtually. It allowed the WP to maintain the scheduled work plan.

WP8 Impact on Long-term Sustainability has the crucial role of integrating all the results achieved in the stakeholder-oriented activities (WP2-6) to maximise the impact on the EPOS Delivery Framework's long-term sustainability guided by EPOS ERIC. WP8 objectives will be reached on a long-term basis, so at M9 was

premature to measure the KPIs. At M27, the KPIs have been measured revealing high performance. Furthermore, KPI 8.3 “number of interactions with the EPOS ERIC GA” with the purpose to measure the number of interactions with the EPOS ERIC General Assembly to monitor the process toward the EPOS Long term sustainability has been added to the KPIs list revealing a very intense dialogue.

In conclusion, some delay in the project performance is mostly due to COVID-19. Considering this aspect, efficient risk management at the WP level is managed through the project risk register as explained in the following paragraph and Annex II.

2. Monitoring of the EPOS SP Risks Register M27

During the 4th EB meeting held on July the 7th, 2021, the EB agreed on again updating the Risk Register, including a COVID-19 dedicated risk to limit the damage caused by the force majeure. Measures to limit the related costs and actions to resume the activities implementation have been planned. The risk has been considered at the WP level, together with the appropriate mitigation actions. The risk consists of the "delay in achieving/delivering milestones and deliverables due to COVID19".

Considering that the Risk Register is a live document, the current update refers to the assessment made at M27 in the framework of the interim report exercise. Risks are assessed, following a three-point scale, to determine their likelihood of occurrence and their possible impact, quantifying the risks exposure calculated with the following formula: Probability x Impact. A three-point scale is used to identify the level of likelihood of occurrence and impact (see Table 1):

Table 1 - Risk likelihood and impact

Scale	Likelihood of occurrence	Impact
1 - Low	Unlikely to occur	Minor impact on time, cost, or quality
2 - Medium	May occur occasionally	Notable impact on time, cost, or quality
3 - High	Is likely to occur	Substantial impact on time, cost, or quality

Considering the risk assessment at M27, the WP Leaders duly implemented mitigation measures to keep risk exposure under control and reduce the likelihood that those risks will happen. COVID-19 significantly affected WP3, and WP5 because of their activities' nature, focusing on cooperation and engagement with stakeholders (e.g., Risk 14 Plan for industry engagement fails".)

There are substantially two aspects to underline after the assessment made at M27:

1. For some of the risks, the level of impact increased with respect to M12, due to the fact that the project is going to an end, and the materialization of the risk could have a higher impact at this stage of the project.
2. A risk has been added to WP2 considering Russia's aggression against Ukraine impacting the organisation of the Brokerage event in the Baltic region.

M27 risk heat is illustrated in the EPOS SP Risk Heat Map.

The updated Risk Register table is included in this document with the Risk Heat Map, respectively, Annex II and Annex III.

ANNEX I – Key Performance Indicators

WP 1 - Project Management						
KPI n.	Description	Objective M1-36	Purpose	Measure tools	M9	M1-27
1.1	Percentage of milestones achieved on time	> 85%	To measure the commitment of the beneficiaries to perform their contractual obligation according to the DoA.	Milestones list and review meeting report	85%	80% Some Milestones have been rescheduled accordingly with the new end date of the project.
1.2	Percentage of interim reports (WP reports and financial reports) submitted on time to the coordinator	> 85%	For the internal monitoring process	Report received	90,63%	100%
1.3	Percentage of beneficiaries attending the PC meetings	> 85%	To measure the commitment of the beneficiaries	Attendance list	87,50%	90%
1.4	Number of EB meetings where decisions are taken	7 (F2F)	To measure the correct implementation of the project	Meeting minutes	5	9
1.5	Percentage of members attending the EB meetings	> 90%	To measure the commitment of WP Leaders	Attendance list	100%	100
1.6	Project intranet: satisfaction rate of the members	High	To measure the efficiency of the internal communication tool	Survey	Not relevant for the period	N/A A survey is planned during the Autumn 2022

WP 2 - Governance and Financial Framework						
KPI n.	Description	Objective	Purpose	Measure tools	M9	M1-27
2.1	Number of engaged national authorities from countries previously involved in EPOS but not yet ERIC members	> 4	Strengthen connections with countries not yet ERIC members	ERIC Membership	1	3
2.2	Number of national authorities engaged from countries not yet involved in EPOS	> 2	Strengthen connections with countries not involved in EPOS	ERIC Membership/NACB members/Observers	6	10
2.3	Number of Meetings of the NACB	> =2	engaging national authorities to follow EPOS ERIC and its delivery framework	Number of meetings and attendance list	1	2
2.4	Percentage of members attending the NACB meetings	> 50%	To measure the interest of the representatives of Countries not members of the ERIC in EPOS	Attendance list	77,78%	80%
2.5	Number of initiatives organized by EPOS ERIC and EPOS Community in the Baltic Region	> 2	Engage scientists and other stakeholders, including data providers from solid Earth science, in the A Baltic region	Attendance list and communities involved	Not relevant for the period	0 Covid-19 restrictions
2.6	Number of initiatives organized by EPOS ERIC and EPOS Community in the A-D-B Region	> 2	Engage scientists and other stakeholders, including data providers from solid Earth science, in the Adriatic-Balkans-Dinarides region	Attendance list and communities involved	Not relevant for the period	2

WP 3 - Global Dimension, European and International Cooperation						
KPI n.	Description	Objective (Target)	Purpose	Measure tools	M9	M1-27
3.1	Number of coordination activities and events to establish and/or strengthen collaboration with other solid-Earth RIs and similar initiatives at an international level	4	To foster collaboration between selected initiatives relevant to the solid Earth domain	Summary report including actions for each coordination activity with relevant global initiatives where EPOS participated	Too early to be measured	20% (severely impacted by COVID-19)
3.2	Number of partnerships established with other solid-Earth RIs and similar initiatives at international level	5	To foster collaboration with other solid-Earth RI at international level	Number of formal partnership agreements (MoU/LoI) with other solid-Earth RIs and similar initiatives at international level.	Too early to be measured	1

WP 3 - Global Dimension, European and International Cooperation

3.3	Number of pan-European thematic initiatives not currently part of EPOS that could contribute to or benefit from becoming part of EPOS.	7	To foster links with pan-European thematic initiatives not currently part of the EPOS RI	List of relevant pan-European thematic initiatives	Too early to be measured	2
3.4	Number of partnerships with relevant national and international institutions, initiatives and research infrastructures in Africa and Latin America working in the solid Earth domain	>3	Develop and document in a white paper the strategy for a coordinated and coherent approach to collaboration with relevant African and Latin American institutions and initiatives in the solid Earth domain	List of relevant institutions and initiatives from Africa and Latin America working in the solid Earth domain	Too early to be measured	Planned output form delayed international conferences
3.5	Number of international meetings and initiatives where EPOS participated	> 6	Community Building	Number of summary report on EPOS participation	Too early to be measured	8 (mostly virtual)
3.6	Number of international meetings and initiatives organised by EPOS	> 2	Community Building	Number of summary reports on activities	Too early to be measured	Not delivered due to COVID-19
3.7	Number of new partnerships with relevant EU-level initiatives that extend the geographical coverage of EPOS Infrastructure	> 2	To measure collaborations established with selected pan-European initiatives	Number of collaboration agreements signed, or in preparation	Too early to be measured	1

WP 4 Increasing value for users

KPI n.	Description	Objective (Target)	Purpose	Measure tools	M9	M1-27	Comments
4.1	Number of tickets resulting from technical audit of ICS code	4/mth. (1hr./tick.)	To increase technical robustness	List of issues to troubleshoot in the ICS code provided by EPOS ERIC (resulting from EPOS IP and other EPOS collateral activities) to the WT. 4.1 Leader	N/A	N/A	The GIT platform is dedicated to tickets collection and traceability.
4.2	Number of services tested and validated in the operational infrastructure	>5	To foster the long-term data integration plan, following the state of the art as advertised in the technical debt document to avoid a. the high probability of collateral effects, resulting in loss of time; b. the difficulty to share knowledge,	Number of data services implemented and validated into the operational platform according to the QA pipeline	>5	>15	3 tsunami, and 6 hazard services have been validated since M9.

			resulting in a small core dev team, which is not sustainable				
4.3	Number of new users' groups (communities at regional or thematic level, laboratories providing TNA services within EPOS Delivery Framework) engaged	4	Tasks 4.2 and 4.3 deal with the engagement of new user groups. The confirmation of their engagement within the duration of the project is a performance indicator of the capacity of the EPOS Delivery Framework to satisfy the expectations of new scientific partners.	New communities integrated within the EPOS Delivery Framework as a consequence of EPOS SP development	2 (>4)	>5	3 Tsunami data groups and 6 hazards joined. The candidate TCS Earthquake has joined. TNA community has agreed to associate their GUI interface to the ICS EPOS data portal. A MoU for the ABD array has been signed.
4.4	Number of GNSS data stakeholders engaged in service integration process	1	The effectiveness and the sustainability of solutions and guidelines provided to the GNSS and the added value of the formalization of the concerned TCS within the EPOS Delivery Framework, will be evaluated by the capacity of engaging new entities of this community to integrate their services and data in EPOS ICS-C	Number of new entities concerned by the GNSS domain, contributing to the Delivery Framework by the provision of new GNSS data or services	About 20	28	
4.5	Number of National Space Agencies engaged	2	To increase and test the sustainability framework of the EPOS Thematic Core Service (TCS)	Number of National Space Agencies not yet involved in EPOS accepting formal link with its Delivery Framework	>2	2	
4.6	Number of successful migration tests with different European cloud computing initiatives	>2	Testing and evaluating the compatibility of EPOS with other cloud computing initiatives, as contribution to a robust sustainability framework for TCS services.	The number of migration experiments within different environments (DIAS, EOSC, etc...) evaluating their capacity to provide sustainable services in the EPOS framework, in terms of: - access speed to the data archive - computing resources performance - computing resources scalability - disk access bandwidth		3	Agreement and design for the experiments still in progress.

				The cost is a distinctive parameter for the sustainability assessment		
4.7	Satisfaction rate of services provided	majority of answers with satisfaction rate > 6	Testing and improving TCS-ICS services for enhanced user experience and trust	Questionnaires dedicated to users engaged in Users Feedback Groups (to test and assess the functionalities and the readiness of the EPOS Delivery Framework) concerning specific elements of the service provided by the platform (both ICS-C and eventually ICS-D). The answers are rated between 1 (negligible) and 10 (very satisfied)	Questionnaires not yet submitted	To be retrieved from POT#6 (July 2022)
4.8	Satisfaction rate of users on the functionalities and readiness of the EPOS Delivery Framework	majority of answers with satisfaction rate > 6	Testing and improving TCS-ICS services for enhanced user experience and trust	Questionnaires dedicated to users engaged in Users Feedback Groups (to test and assess the functionalities and the readiness of the EPOS Delivery Framework) concerning specific elements of the GUI, the implemented functionalities, and the usability. The answers are rated between 1 (negligible) and 10 (very satisfied)	Questionnaires not yet submitted	To be retrieved from POT#6 (July 2022)

WP 5 - Strengthening Links with Private Sector						
KPI n.	Description	Objective M1-39	Purpose	Measure tools	M9	M1-27
5.1.1	Carrying out outreach programs targeting the private sector	20	To measure the potential of pilots to attract the private and public organizations; to allow to react and improve the pilots during the project	Number of commercial organizations to whom the pilot services/pilot areas have been presented, registration to the workshops	(4): EGW2020 (strong participation of private sector), KGHM, PMG, Lubelski Węgiel Bogdanka	(17): IMO workshop, Turów, Geodays, Gas Storage PL, Enritt, Czech-Slov conf, ICS HPC ACK
5.1.2		4	To promote the EPOS assets and field of expertise within the private sector stakeholders	Sessions/meetings/workshops organized outside EPOS promoting the collaboration of EPOS-private sector	3	8
5.1.3		2	To promote the EPOS and EPOS services within the private sector stakeholders and other group of stakeholders	Number of published articles about the EPOS, EPOS services for innovation and pilot areas	1	7
5.1.4		4 10	Building innovation network - identify accessible units, to serve the needs for information of the business community	Number of formal links with other initiatives with the membership of private sector; Number of the companies in the database of industry stakeholders	3 (ENRIICT, IAC TCS AH, VAAC) 10	3

5.2.1	Building the governance/legal framework	8	To map the innovation activities and expectations in EPOS community	Number of meetings with EPOS SP project leaders to collect material for case studies of collaborations between EPOS and the private sector.	9	9
5.2.2		4	To define principles and descriptions of procedures to be followed for dealings with the private sector; to ensure consistency of policy and harmonization of relevant procedures throughout EPOS	Number of case studies of cooperation with the private sector based on EPOS infrastructure described and analysed from a legal perspective	4	4
5.2.3		3	To establish and review strategies and scenarios and possible legal frameworks for cooperation with the private sector	Number of meetings with EPOS ERIC representatives	0	1
5.3.1	Boosting EPOS to measure the effect of innovation activities	1	Proposing parameters to measure the success of innovation impact	KPIs to measure the effect of the innovation activities after EPOS SP project finishes	0	0
5.3.2		1	Building and promoting the incubation potential of EPOS	Number of cross-functional, cross-disciplinary teams that can take high-potential ideas to fusion, from pilot area/prototype to demonstrate/business case, e.g., DT- GEO – TRL 6, at the national level, e.g., EPOS PL+, EPOS SE, EPOS FIN	1 (the national initiative EPOS PL+ aiming to develop services for the science-private sector)	3 EPOS PL+, EPOS SE, DT- GEO
5.3.3		1	Enunciating and publicising information about the EPOS innovation services, experts and innovation activities for both sides: EPOS community and private sector.	Recommendations/design for R&D portal for private sector and for EPOS community	0	1

WP 6 Value for society						
KPI n.	Description	Objective (Target)	Purpose	Measure tools	M9	M1-27
6.1	Degree of awareness for ethical principles among EPOS services	high	Reaching a high degree of awareness for ethical principles among EPOS services.	Report based on a collection of existing ethical principles and supplemented by a survey.	On track	High
6.2	Amount of EPOS products and services relevant for seismic hazard and risk	medium	Measuring the amount of products and services relevant for seismic hazard and risk.	Qualitative and quantitative survey	On track	medium
6.3	Degree of awareness of EPOS core services to adhere FAIR principles	high	Reaching a high degree of awareness of EPOS services to adhere FAIR principles.	Survey	On track	These activities are significantly delayed due to staff shortages. A plan to complete the actions has been implemented and communicated to the EB.

WP 7 Outreach and Training							
KPI n.	Description	Objective (Target)	Purpose	Measure tools	M9	M1-27	Comments
7.1	Training: Number of training sessions	3	Contributing to the usage of the EPOS contents / services / Engaging stakeholders	Training plan	3	12	NSS + Nordic EPOS annual workshop, EPOS-N Portal training (2x), TCS Tsunami Training.
7.2	Training: Number of industrial users involved in trainings	3	Contributing to the usage of the EPOS contents / services / Engaging stakeholders	Participant lists	4	6	It can be measured by M18. There were no industry representatives present during the M19-27 training sessions.
7.3	Training: Number of researchers involved in trainings	40	Contributing to the usage of the EPOS contents / services / Engaging stakeholders	Participant lists	107	504	
7.4	Training: Number of early career scientists and students involved in trainings	30	Contributing to the usage of the EPOS contents / services / Engaging stakeholders	Participant lists	30	50	
7.5	Training: Number of questionnaires submitted (within six months after the training)	50	Contributing to the usage of the EPOS contents / services / Engaging stakeholders	Questionnaire	41	138	
7.6	Training: Number of views of each training video	30	Maximize dissemination of EPOS results	Analytics	190	727	
7.7	Training: Number of tutorial documents opened/downloaded	30	Maximize dissemination of EPOS results	Analytics	N/A	N/A	
7.8	Outreach: Number of outreach events	3	Maximize dissemination of EPOS results	report	4	12	NSS +Nordic EPOS annual workshop, EPOS-N Portal training (2x), TCS Tsunami Training.
7.9	Outreach: Number of industrial users attending the events	15	Maximize dissemination of EPOS results	Participant lists	4	6	There were 2 events in autumn 2021 where

							industry representatives could be present. TBC
7.10	Outreach: Number of researchers attending the events	300	Maximize dissemination of EPOS results	Participant lists	107	608	Slovenia event, BGS Congr., EPOS-NL
7.11	Outreach: Number of early career scientists and students attending the events	100	Maximize dissemination of EPOS results	Participant lists	30	155	iEarth event (Norway)
7.12	Outreach: Number of government Officials attending the events	20	Maximize dissemination of EPOS results	Participant lists	N/A	1	Possible participation during the event in Slovenia and BGS - TBC.
7.13	Outreach: Number of participants from the targeted regions	100	Maximize dissemination of EPOS results	Participant lists	38	3+	Baltic region + Balkan region
7.14	Outreach: Number of participants from existing thematic groups	100	Maximize dissemination of EPOS results	Participant lists	107	375	NSS + Nordic EPOS annual workshop, EPOS-N Portal training (2x), TCS Tsunami Training.
7.15	Outreach: Number of participants from new thematic groups	40	Maximize dissemination of EPOS results	Participant lists	NA	60	NSS + Nordic EPOS annual workshop, EPOS-N Portal training (2x), TCS Tsunami Training.
7.16	Outreach: Number of outreach materials	7	Maximize EPOS communication and dissemination of results	Report on Dissemination and communication materials	3	14	Due to the pandemic, the majority of new materials was produced in 2021 and 2022, when participation in physical events returned.
7.16.1	Number of Brochure (per year/ per target audience)	1	Maximize EPOS communication and dissemination of results	Report on Dissemination and communication materials	NA	1	Produce one new brochure by the end of the project.
7.16.2	Number of Flyers (per year)	4	Maximize EPOS communication and dissemination of results	Report on Dissemination and communication materials	1	8/ year average	8/ year average (16 total: 10 new flyers in 2021 and 6 new flyers in 2022)
7.16.3	Number of leaflet/posters (each event)	2	Maximize EPOS communication and dissemination of results	Report on Dissemination and communication materials	2	2	

7.17	EPOS website -percentage of unique new visitors of 10 most visited pages (per year)	40%	Maximize EPOS communication and dissemination of results	google analytics/report of dissemination & communication - qualitative analysis	88%	78%	
7.18	D&C: SP website pages - number of views/unique new visitors (monthly average)	20	Maximize EPOS communication and dissemination of results	Analytics	1310/866	214 / 119 (monthly average)	EPOS SP new pages were created in Feb 2022
7.19	Social media - Twitter - Number of SP tweets (monthly average)	8	Maximize EPOS communication and dissemination of results	twitter stats/Analytics	12 in tot, 1,333 monthly avg.)	188 Total (7 average)	
7.20	Social media - Twitter - Number of impressions of SP tweets / qualitative analysis of new followers /	high /expected/ Low	Maximize EPOS communication and dissemination of results	twitter stats/Analytics	low	Expected	
7.21	social media - Facebook SP - number of posts related to SP (monthly average)	8	Maximize EPOS communication and dissemination of results	google analytics	3	7 (monthly average)	
7.22	social media - LinkedIn SP - number of posts related to SP	8	Maximize EPOS communication and dissemination of results	google analytics	0	0	
7.23	social media - YouTube SP - number of videos created by SP (webinars- tutorial- e-learning, trainings- use cases - interviews))	10	Maximize EPOS communication and dissemination of results	report on Dissemination and communication materials	2	12	
7.24	Number of visualisations of SP videos on YouTube	100	Maximize EPOS communication and dissemination of results	google Analytics	0	1149	Number of views from EPOS training channel videos + EPOS generic video
7.25	Newsletter - Number of SP articles (per year)	8	Maximize EPOS communication and dissemination of results	mail Chimp statistics	0	2	
7.26	Number of Scientific publications linked to EPOS SP project	2	Maximize EPOS communication and dissemination of results	Publications suggested by Open AIRE / EU portal, continuous reporting	2	10	

WP8 Impact on Long-term sustainability							
KPI n.	Description	Objective (Target)	Purpose	Measure tools	M9	M1-27	Comments
8.1	Percentage of service providers having completed the questionnaire (Linked to WP2)	80%	Sustainability of service provision	service providers contacted + questionnaires completed	N/A	88%; 44 responses out of 50 (unique SP from Cost Book)	
8.2	Percentage of contacted data providers having completed the questionnaire	30%	Sustainability of data provision	data providers contacted + questionnaires completed	N/A	88 responses	All data providers are not identified yet.
8.3	Number of interactions with the EPOS ERIC GA	High	EPOS Sustainability long-term	Number of GA meetings	N/A	11 out of 11 meetings	

ANNEX II – The EPOS SP Risk Register (M27)

¹⁾LoO=Likelihood of occurrence: 1-Low; 2-Medium; 3-High; ²⁾Imp.=Impact: 1-Minor; 2-Notable; 3-Substantial.

a	b	c	d	e	f	g	h	i	j	k	l	m
Risk No	Description	WP	Risk Mitigation Measures	¹⁾ LoO (M9)	²⁾ Imp. (M9)	Risk Heat (M9)	¹⁾ LoO (M18)	²⁾ Imp. (M18)	Risk Heat (M18)	¹⁾ LoO (M27)	²⁾ Imp. (M27)	Risk Heat (M27)
1	Failure to reach the objectives on time and on budget.	WP1	Careful monitoring of the task progress and early identification of the problems that may arise will be assessed by the Project Coordinator and the ECO.	1	2		1	2		1	2	
2	Communication within the project is not sufficient.	WP1	The coordinator will set up more face2face meetings and teleconferences to increase the cross-fertilization in the project.	1	2		1	2		1	2	
3	Poor performance of partners.	WP1	The contingency plan is activated in case a partner submits the work with a delay of more than a week (from the internal deadline) without justification. The partner is asked to justify the delay and set a new deadline. If this situation is repeated, then the EB will discuss and decide on appropriate measures.	1	2		1	3		1	3	
4	Delays in the project timetable.	WP1	The PC agrees and applies contingency plans including (i) re-allocation of resources, (ii) parallel execution of tasks, and (iii) re-scheduling of activities.	2	2		2	2		2	2	
5	Turnover of staff at partner Institutions.	WP1	Participating institutions have a duty to respect the contract with the European Commission and ensure the completion of work. Partners will have the responsibility to inform the coordinator timely of such an event and ensure proper handover of the job. Finally, the transfer of a certain task to other team members with relevant expertise can be considered to carry out the corresponding tasks.	3	2		3	2		3	2	

6	Conflict between Partners.	WP1	Legally binding consortium agreement. Mediation by Coordinator.	2	2		2	2		1	2	
7	Non-acceptable quality of the deliverables.	WP1	There is a procedure in the proposed project management schema, based on the review of deliverables by the WP Leader and the ECO to guarantee the quality of the final deliverables.	1	1		1	1		1	1	
8	Failure in engaging National Authorities.	WP2	Foster the establishment of national consortia, Joint Research Units, and engagement of national teams.	2	2		2	2		1	2	
9	Failure in identifying mechanisms for the in-kind contributions through national funds.	WP2	Interact with TCS Boards and ERIC Members to support harmonization of national efforts to financially support EPOS operation through IKC. (rev. amendment)	2	3		2	3		2	3	
10	Lack of engagement from solid Earth Research Infrastructures and similar related initiatives in other regions.	WP3	Establish links with relevant global coordinating activities and initiatives to establish channels of communication and foster collaboration e.g., Research Data Alliance (RDA), One Geology, ICSU-WDS.	2	1		1	2		1	2	
11	Poor attendance at the planned Conferences, especially from stakeholders in Africa and Latin America.	WP3	Ensure the locations for these conferences are accessible as possible for stakeholders from these regions. Engage with local organisers at an early stage to promote and encourage participation.	2	2		2	2		2	2	
12	Delay in providing plan and guidelines for engaging new communities.	WP4	Planning of new communities will be supported by other EPOS ERIC and other WPs.	1	1		2	2		1	1	
13	Missed information dissemination between WP participants which would lead to overall delay.	WP4	The User Value Board will focus on a high level of delegation from WP Leader to task manager and improve communication efficiency. The work package will leverage the tools and workflows used in EPOS IP when feasible.	1	1		2	1		1	1	
14	Plan for industry engagement fails.	WP5	Revise plan rapidly taking advice from industry and from other projects.	2	2		3	3		3	3	

15	Governance of EPOS relationship with Private Sector unacceptable to Private Sector.	WP5	Revise governance in accordance with wishes of industry and experience of other projects with advice from EPOS legal team.	1	2		2	3		2	3	
16	Pilots fail technically or otherwise do not convince industry.	WP5	Redefine pilot to ensure success and engage with industry to gain greater cooperation.	1	2		1	2		1	2	
17	Industry has no interest in EPOS Research and Innovation Services.	WP5	Engage other industry sectors – especially ICT – to gain interest and hence sustainability.	2	2		2	3		2	3	
18	Lack of response to consultation / interaction requests from stakeholders external to EPOS.	WP6	Start requesting input/feedback as early as possible, use established direct links between WP partners and relevant externals to gather feedback.	1	2		1	2		1	2	
19	Lack of response to consultation / interaction requests from stakeholders internal to EPOS.	WP6	Start requesting input/feedback as early as possible, utilize EPOS meetings to directly engage with relevant individuals, engage the EPOS management in requesting feedback.	1	3		1	2		1	3	
20	Fail to engage participation from targeted regions.	WP7	Identify the reasons for missing engagement after the first workshops and events and adopt alternative measures in the following planned activities.	2	1		1	2		1	1	
21	Fail to engage participation from the new Thematic Core Services (TCS) (medium).	WP7	Identify the reasons for missing engagement after the first workshops and events and adopt alternative measures in the following planned activities.	2	2		2	2		2	2	
22	Insufficient information flow from WP2-7 (low).	WP8	Risk-mitigation: dedicated face-to-face meeting members to facilitate interactions.	1	3		1	3		2	3	
23	Lack of engagement of data providers for landscape analysis on data provision (medium).	WP8	Interaction with General Assembly and NACB members to facilitate interactions.	2	2		2	2		2	3	

U1	Delays in implementing TCS services in the EPOS infrastructure, mainly due to unexpected development demand and unavailability of IT development resources.	WP4	The "TCS-ICS interactions team "provides a roadmap & prioritization of development needs, structured in pitches according to "Shape Up" methodology, that allows to verify and adequately plan and distribute ICS and TCS IT human resources. If this risk becomes effective, the ICS-TCS can reschedule activities and resources by reviewing the priority list of pitches.	1	3		2	3		1	3	
U2	Products of the various tasks result too heterogeneous and incongruent with the requirements and expectations of WP8.	WP4	An internal document including a questionnaire and a schedule of internal intermediate deliverables, transversal to the different tasks of WP4, is agreed with WP8 leader and shared among WP4 Task leaders.	1	2		1	2		1	2	
U3	Lack of alignment of expectations between EPOS SP/EPOS ERIC, especially regarding the information from other WPs to include in the Long-Term Sustainability Plan.	WP8	Coordination through EB, dedicated meetings within WP8, ad hoc meetings WP8 leader/EPOS ERIC to adjust alignment whenever needed.	2	3		1	2		2	3	
U4	Delay in achieving and/or delivering milestones and deliverables due to COVID19 pandemic.	All WPs	The coordinator requests all the WP leaders to include a risk linked to COVID-19 in the internal risk register, identify and apply a relevant mitigation measure within each WP. Contingency plans will be implemented if needed.	2	3		2	3		2	3	
U5	Russia-Ukraine war impact on the organisation of the Brokerage event in the Baltic region.	WP2	Integration of the virtual communication tools in the implementation of WP2 activities	N/A	N/A		N/A	N/A		3	2	

Unforeseen Risks per WP

a	b	c	d	e	f	g	h	i		J	K	I
Risk No U4	Description	WP	Risk Mitigation Measures	¹ Lo O M9	² Impa ct M9	Risk Heat M9	¹ LoO M18	² Imp. M18	Risk Heat M18	¹ LoO M27	² Impa ct M27	Risk Heat M27
	Delay in achieving and/or delivering milestones and deliverables due to the COVID19 pandemic.	WP1	The coordinator requests all the WP leaders to include a risk linked to COVID-19 in the internal risk register, identify and apply a relevant mitigation measure within each WP. Contingency plans will be implemented if needed.	2	3		2	3		3	3	
	Delay in achieving and/or delivering milestones and deliverables due to COVID19 pandemic.	WP2	1. Integrating the virtual communication tools in the implementation of WP2 activities 2. Strengthening the communication with WP8	2	3		1	3		3	2	
	Delay in achieving and/or delivering milestones and deliverables due to COVID19 pandemic.	WP3	Starts remote promotional activities to create momentum around the EPOS Conferences.	2	3		3	2		3	2	
	Delay in achieving and/or delivering milestones and deliverables due to COVID19 pandemic.	WP4	The WP leader informs the LP and proposes a new deadline, paying attention to limit and mitigate the impacts on other project activities	2	3		1	3		1	3	
	Delay in achieving and/or delivering milestones and deliverables due to COVID19 pandemic.	WP5	Acknowledging the missed deadline and resulting delay as soon as possible; Identifying and evaluating the alternatives.	2	3		3	3		3	3	
	Delay in achieving and/or delivering milestones and deliverables due to COVID19 pandemic.	WP6	Best effort to compensate despite the difficult circumstances	2	3		1	3		1	3	
	Delay in achieving and/or delivering milestones and deliverables due to COVID19 pandemic.	WP7	Identify there are delays in deliverables and find out the reasons for possible delays.	2	3		2	3		1	3	

	<p>Delay in achieving and/or delivering milestones and deliverables due to COVID19 pandemic.</p>	<p>WP8</p>	<p>Discussions within WP + interaction with EB and ECO to replace face to face meetings with virtual meetings. When there's a better overview of the pandemic situation, face to face meetings could be rescheduled.</p>	<p>2</p>	<p>3</p>							
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Annex III

The EPOS SP Risk Heat Map (M27 – April 2022)

EPOS SP Risk Heat Map (M24 - January 2022) - Milestone 21

EPOS SP Risk Heat Map (M12 – January 2021)

